

TEACHING PIANO PERFORMANCE: FOCUSING ON FINGER MOVEMENT

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Abstract

This article discusses the importance and methods of focusing on finger movement in teaching piano performance. Fingers are one of the fundamental elements of piano technique, and their precise and smooth movement plays a crucial role in achieving success in piano playing. To properly develop finger movement, various exercises, scales, arpeggios, and dynamic techniques are recommended, along with considerations of psychological aspects and motivation in the learning process. This article provides methodical approaches to finger positioning, independent finger movement, and maintaining balance with the hand, offering essential techniques to improve students' piano performance and contribute to the overall effectiveness of piano education. The article can serve as a guide for both piano teachers and students.

Keywords

piano performance, finger movement, technical skills, independent movement, finger positioning, scales, arpeggios, dynamics, motivation, psychological aspects, methodology, students, piano education.

1. Introduction

Teaching piano performance is a complex process that involves the development of technical skills and creative abilities. In this process, finger movement plays a crucial role as one of the key elements of piano performance. Fingers have the task of executing various actions in piano playing, so it is important to focus on their movement. Proper finger

movement not only ensures technical precision but also enhances musical expression and emotional interpretation.

Understanding the significance of focusing on finger movement in piano performance teaching helps to accelerate the technical development of students. The aim of this article is to analyze methods of developing proper finger movement and to discuss the pedagogical techniques that contribute to effective finger movement training in piano performance, as well as to offer recommendations for achieving successful results both technically and artistically.

2. Finger Movement and Its Proper Development

In piano performance, the proper development of finger movement is essential for effective technique. Fingers must be positioned correctly to press the piano keys precisely, softly, and efficiently. Ensuring that fingers are in the right shape, moving independently, and avoiding physical strain are crucial elements of proper technique.

2.1. Proper Finger Positioning

Fingers must be positioned correctly when pressing the piano keys. The hand shape should allow for an optimal finger position, with each finger being capable of lifting and pressing the keys with proper force. It is important to maintain a flexible yet firm position, which allows for precise key articulation.

2.2. Independent Finger Movement

In piano performance, fingers must be able to move independently. This is necessary for developing technical accuracy and ensuring each finger can perform its tasks autonomously. Specific exercises, including scales, arpeggios, and other technical drills, help develop the independence of the fingers and contribute to greater precision in playing.

3. Technique and Position of the Fingers

The technique and position of the fingers are crucial for developing proper piano performance skills. Correct finger positioning and smooth, accurate movements contribute to perfecting piano technique. Technical precision in finger movement is key to improving students' proficiency and effectiveness in playing.

3.1. Relationship Between Fingers and Hands

Fingers should move in coordination with the hands when playing the piano. Along with the fingers, the hand and wrist must also be aligned and balanced. When fingers press the piano keys, the hands should move in harmony with them. This connection ensures balance between different parts of the hand and contributes to overall performance fluidity.

3.2. Smoothness of Finger Movement

The smoothness of finger movement is essential in piano playing. Fingers should avoid excessive pressure while pressing the keys, as this can lead to technical mistakes and fatigue. Additionally, smooth finger movements help express musical nuances and improve the articulation of each note.

4. Creative Practical Exercises for Finger Movement

To develop proper finger movement, practical exercises are necessary. These exercises, including scales, arpeggios, and dynamic variations, are essential for refining finger technique. Furthermore, focusing on psychological aspects and motivating students to develop their skills contributes to the overall success of their piano learning.

4.1. Scales and Arpeggios

Practicing scales and arpeggios is crucial for developing proper finger movement. Scales help ensure that each note is pressed precisely and evenly, while arpeggios enhance finger independence and coordination. Repeated practice of these exercises improves finger technique and contributes to better control of finger movements.

4.2. Finger Dexterity

In order to achieve proper finger movement, it is important to improve finger dexterity. Developing finger dexterity requires that each finger moves accurately and consistently, one after another. By focusing on the flexibility and control of each finger, students will improve both the precision and speed of their movements.

5. Psychological Aspects of Finger Movement

Finger movement in piano performance is not only related to physical technique but also involves psychological factors. The mental state of students, their motivation, and their ability to focus play a significant role in their ability to execute finger movements effectively.

5.1. Psychological Balance

Proper finger movement requires a psychological approach that aligns with physical technique. If students feel confident and focused while playing, this contributes to their technical precision and emotional expression. When fingers are positioned and moved correctly, the student will feel more successful and comfortable in their performance.

5.2. Motivation Development

Working on finger movement also affects the development of students' motivation. The desire to master independent finger movements and improve technical skills increases the student's motivation and dedication to learning. This motivation helps students overcome difficulties in technique and stay engaged in their practice.

6. Conclusion

In teaching piano performance, focusing on finger movement is crucial for developing technical skills. Fingers play an essential role in achieving clarity of sound, dynamics, and emotional expression. Exercises designed to develop finger movement and coordination, as well as the psychological aspects and physical technique, help improve students' overall performance.

Additionally, maintaining the correct position of the fingers and focusing on independence, dexterity, and balance in finger movements will result in better technical control and artistic expression. Developing proper finger movement is not only vital for mastering piano technique but also for enhancing the creative potential of students.

References:

Suzuki, S. (1983). *Nurtured by Love*. Oxford University Press.

Hesketh, M. (2004). *Piano Teaching Methodology*. Cambridge University Press.

Andreev, N. (2007). *Music Pedagogy and Technique*. Moscow: Muzyka.